

The Coupling Constants Series – Majestic (3) Enigma

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April 4, 2021

Abstract:

The paper suggesting three different options concerning the rule of the invariant three which appear at each term of the coupling constants series. analysis of each option alongside the meaning of each option is presented.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

The **Invariant three (3) as a cause**. Notice that all the element within the closed term (8*..) Are two and three divisible to vanish into matter. The invariant (3) prevents it completely and then as a result, a net variation will appear. The net variation is proportional to the right element in the bracket $(8 * 3) \propto 3$ and $(24 * 5) \propto 5$.

Option two - The invariant three (3) as a result-There are perfect clusters of variations such $(8 * 3), (24 * 5)$, which experience additional net variation causing them to destabilize. The result is manifested in the invariant (3). The additional variation could affect them could be external. Less likeable option. It is less likeable as we can them create mixtures $(8*3)$ to destabilize by five net variations, and yield invariant (3) and all the beauty in which we attained than will be lost.

Option 3 - The **Invariant three (3) and net variation as duals**-both appear at the same time and they are related to each other by more fundamental relation, which is not attainable nor explainable. Even though we found a jewel, many questions still stand unanswered.

Why the invariant (3) appear as it is and do not change? Of course, that the real answer to that question is that one does not know. However, one can guess and say that (3) is the smallest odd prime. If we assume that nature is Lagrangian oriented, it might be the minimal way to destabilize the cluster of potential matter. Why add (37) additional variations when only (3) is needed? Its a logical argument not a proof, and therefore rightfully argued by reader. One was trying to argue that (3) is a Prime minima, that is the reason for its invariant in the series. Remember that even variations vanish, so two is not an option.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)